

Functioning of Turkic Elements in Modern Hindi

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Abstract—It is discussed about modern usage of adopted words and their vocabularies, Turkism usage fields, phonetic, grammatical and lexis-semantic assimilation of the typological-morphological structures of entering to different Hindi languages in comparative typological aspects in this scientific article. The lexis vocabulary is rich, the prevalence area is wide and it has researched the entering process of vocabulary into the great languages of Turkic elements from the speakers' numbers. The research work has worked on the base of Hindi vocabulary.

Keywords—Adopted words, language communications, Turkism, Turkic languages.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN modern Kazakh language and linguo-cultural science the role of the language cultures and to influence culture in the formation of language, it is increasing the actuality of the problems and is considering in spread volume. Having thousand years history of Turkic and Indian cultural communications and stayed "sign" undoubtedly in these languages. The actuality of this scientific article is to determine the adopted elements of Hindi vocabulary; it has come out after discussing the peculiarities of the language. To research Hindi language vocabulary is to know about the communication problems of other nations and cultures. It has reformed the language communication theory in the base of the actuality of historical problems.

Turkic language is spread in large areas and communicates with many languages around, and is continuing to communicate yet. It is a reason of modern and old Indian language, its communication with other languages and their history and to research in scientific ways is not depend on to Indian history, it has scientific importance of the history of neighbors' languages. The problems of communication history of Turkic languages with other languages of the world, the Hindi communicates with other languages requires to consider them in detail. Vocabulary is the most inclined field

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of inflexion; there are more lexis interchanges than other elements. If we pay attention to every language vocabulary, not every element changes in definite time. There are permanents and changeable in it. However, it concerns to relative names, body names and common names connecting with everyday life and others in some of permanent theme groups. And the verb is more permanent than noun, even it's the category, which doesn't change from one language into other. The formation of adopted words is legal process, the result of people's cultural, economical and political connections to each other. It is one of the factors of development to enter the adopted words from other languages.

"The linguistics dictionary" which published under the guidance of E.D. Suleimenova, she gives the definition that "Turkism is entering from Turkic language and that is the word or word formation, which is known strange element of other language" [1].

In V. D. Arakin's opinion, Turkism is from kind of Turkic languages, has no origin, the words, which included straight into other languages [2].

Ancient Turkic tribes are only followed after human civilization, not only a consumer of another civilization products, it wasn't little time, that they were leaders and the hearth of the human civilization. The one of the bright descriptions is the Turkic civilization influence into the development of Indian culture. The language of Turkic people stayed the sign in the vocabularies of many world languages, especially in Hindi language.

II. DISCUSSION

The historical and cultural factors of Turkism in Hindi

At the beginning of IX century Turkic invaders began to open the war with their sacred flag to India. Spending the Feudal division time the Indian princes couldn't stand before this attack, time by time Great Deli Sultan formed, who managed the Muslim invaders in the north part of India.

Turkic tribes gave the chance to communicate with local tribes jointly, especially in the lexis field. The lexis of mixed languages in Deli Sultan was given clearly in the middle century scientist Badr-Addin Ibrahim's work "Farhanguya Zafanguya va jahanpuya" (Speaking vocabulary and world reading). The bright sight of the relation of Turkic and Indian language is growing the scientific interest to the word value and materials nowadays. It was entered the words from modern Kazakh language, like *brother*, *fiancé*, *root*, *sister-in-law*.

Entering the Muslim army to India did not give to appear the new language, although it influenced for the development

of other languages: at first, Indian people communicate with the invaders of other languages and they always add new words into their language vocabulary; in the second joining the huge places of North India and they improved the language in one region, because the usage of language were spread by central power spacious. This dialect of Khari-boli came from Hindustani language. There are few Turkic elements in Hindustani. The Turkic language included to India by speakers of that language. Great Mongol Imperia founder Babyr wrote his native language in Shagatai language.

The scientist in Aurazeb palace and his protector of science, culture and literature field Mukhammed Yakub Dzhanghi's work "Kelur nama", Shagatai-Persian language vocabulary were composed by the command of Aurazeb. "Kelur nama" vocabulary is the important source to learn Uzbek old language.

To introduce the contents of "Kelur nama", we understood that, this work is for Shagatai language grammar and vocabulary in XVII century in India. The introduction of "Kelur nama" is in Persian and old Uzbek language signs showed the usage of old Uzbek language among the Indian leaders (rulers). Mukhammed Yakub Dzhanghi gave the following concept about his book: "Collected old information about Turkic languages and it is either clear to understand for readers, or useful grammatical rules and this vocabulary appeared in the purpose in order to use easily" [3].

Central Asian people paid more attention for "Kelur nama" as an important literary memorial in XX century in 20 years. In the introduction of new publication of the vocabulary this new vocabulary of "Turkic language" called as an important textbook after Mahmud Kashkari's vocabulary.

The invasions were for India from Central East countries, the state was established by the Muslim invaders and the Islam extended wide, they were great influenced to India culture and literature. The one of the historicist of that time was from the cities Deli to Bagdad, Egypt, New Constantinople by Zia ad-din Baranin's legend works [4].

The adopted words are the represents of historic-cultural communication having many century histories. The different structure of Turkic language and Hindi language vocabulary units we can conclude in changing by the geographical, cultural, historical and social factors.

The lexical-semantic groups of Turkic language in Hindi

The people's cultural sign has shown through the language. Although the language is soft, its nature is difficult, because the world picture describes different in human language. The national language vocabulary recourses are always developing and enlarging. The language lexis are enlarging and increasing with new words in the language, culture communication.

क़ोरमा (qavurma) – fried meat [5]. Fried meat – carved and fried meat [6].

The word *Fried // fried meat* have brought to India as a name of new meal from Turkic country with the wide field and many animals.

The word कुरता (kurta) - jacket, shirt [5] is the national clothing of Indian men *dkhoti* (like a sari, which men wear round waist), although it is not very comfortable, then with the necessary to close all the body "kurta pajama" got in to the men's clothes with Muslim's, because it is light, soft and convenient clothing in hot weather. The shirt is the men's surface clothing [7].

The incomer words of Turkic language to Hindi have the similar meanings; the synonyms appeared in the result of this.

Turkic adopted words with the synonyms: बैरक (bairaq) - झंदा (j^handa) – flag; एल्ची (elci) – राजदुत (rajdut) – ambassador, emissary.

The Hindi language from Turkic words considers the human life in different ways. They are: the necessary domestic demands, foods, relatives, the name of clothes, army terminology and etc.

The necessary domestic demands:

कैंची [qainci] – scissors, चाकू [caku] – knife, चिलमची [cilamci] – basin, plates and dishes, बरमा [barma] – rill.

The name of foods:

क़वुरमा (qavurma) – fried meat, समोस (samosa) – three-corned pastry, बुजा [buza] – shindy, beer. As we know like Russian word *kefir* is the Turkic word from root, however केफिर [kefor] – airan, पुलाव [pulau] – pulaw.

The name of relatives:

आगा [ağa] - brother, दादा [dada] - daddy, father, आपा [apa] – senior sister, बीबी [bibi] - wife, partner, आबा [aba] – father.

The name of clothers:

कुरता [kurta] - shirt, cardigan, कुरती [kurti] - blouse, sleeveless jacket (woman's), चोगा [coğa] – dressing gown, knitted sleeve clothing from camel's fur.

One of evident place among the Turkic words of the incomer language to Hindi is army vocabulary. For example: तमनचा [tamanca] - pistol, तोप [top] – gun.

The Kazakh word *orda* in Hindi has two meanings. The first is उर्दू [Urdu] – army, army camp in male gender, the second is Urdu language in female gender. The meaning of the word is far army word and language titles from Kazakh. The following meaning is given about the word *Orda* in the Kazakh short etymological dictionary:

The word *Orda* is common for many Turkic languages, in some time their Nomad tribes, the name of unity and the place, where is the unity leaders centre. For example, it was the place, where ran the khan and leaders: *Ak Orda*, *Altyn Orda* and others. In our opinion, from meaning of the word *orda*, where the army collected much time appeared from the meanings of army and arm. The meaning of the word *Orda* had kept in Turkic and Azerbaijan languages. The word *Orda*

changed to Russian and gave the meanings of armed power, conquerors and invaders [8].

In Modern Kazakh language the word *karaul* (*guard*) has many meanings, which can use in war resources. 1) troops, small army sub-division; 2) the target instrument for skirmish; 3) guard, watch.

The word *guard* means, that is the army guard, who goes in front of the army and informs all the information, which he saw and knew [9].

This word came to Hindi from the army meaning. In Hindi and Russian dictionaries किरावल [qiraval] - guard, front line.

कराबीन [qarabon] – the word carbine is used widely in army vocabulary, certainly it uses in Russian language without changes.

Turkism phonetic assimilation

It is known that every language has own internal rights. The phoneme quality of one language is possible to change from one language into another. The Turkic words income into Hindi, they are depends on phonetic rights, they changed their first phonetic form with the action.

Oral income words, used and perceptible language dialects are marked by the peculiarities of changing forms. For example, the word *guard* has 5 phonetic original words in Hindi: किरावल [qiraval], हरावल [qaraval], करावल [haraval], हारौल [haroul], हिरावल [hiraval].

The graphical and phonetic originals appeared to show the adopted words assimilation of level. For example, the meaning of the word *basin* in Hindi is चिलमची [cilam-ci], without [ɪ] letters in Hindi and was changed to the letter [u], the letter [u] was changed to the letter [ɪ], the letter *n* destroyed and stayed in चिलमची *cilam-ci*. The word *Sign* has two phonetic originals in Hindi. 1. तग्मा [tamga], 2. तगमा [tagma]. The word *gung, robber* has three originals in Hindi dictionary. They are: कज्जाक [qazzaq], कजाक [qazak] and कजाख [qazak^h], *brother, owner* has two originals.

When Turkic elements changes into Hindi, obeying their internal rights of that language and have met to different phonetic changes. However, it is clear, that Hindi and Turkic languages have own phonetic rights in two different language system.

If we pay attention to Turkic vowels, there are many Turkic sounds without equivalents of Hindi languages. The *ə, ɣ, ɤ, ɐ, ɪ, i* sounds from vowels, [ɣ] sound from consonants have no equivalents. The main and basic requirements of the formal descriptions of the words are phonetic substance, that is to say foreign words in the Hindi sounds. The scientists said about this phenomenon: "...in all languages, there are relatively difficult for the sounds pronunciation of sounds combination, which every language tends to be free as possible and make them easier for the pronunciation of sounds and combinations of sounds" [10].

It can say in conditional the sound *ə* has no equivalents in Hindi. The professor M.Tomanov said about it: "To compare the vowel phonemes of ancient Turkic sounds in the structure of the root words, the phoneme source, which have seen different is *ə*. In the VI-VIII century in language signs, there is no much kind of morphemes in the signs of the first time of Middle Ages. The [ə] phoneme of Turkic language has true recommendation forming from the East languages than Kazakh factors" [11].

That's why it has a doubt for right recommendation that the phoneme [ə] came from Eastern languages. The Turkic word *father* आबा [aba] is given as sound [a] in Hindi language.

Turkic language with the phoneme [e] was changed with the following phonemes, the sound [e] in Kazakh words:

e – अ [a] father – aba, jacket – kurta; e – इ [i] carpet – galica; e – [ऐ] [ai] fence - qaitun.

In place of phoneme [O]:

o – उ [u] orda – urdu, bag – bukca, shindy – buza, joy – hush.

In place of phoneme [U]:

u – ओ [o] fried meat - horma; u – अ [a] guard – haraval.

In place of phoneme [ɣ]: ɣ – अ [a] drill – barma; ɣ – उ [y] socks - jurrab.

In place of phoneme [ɪ]: ɪ – अ [a] drill – barma, guard – haraval, food, fare – sougat; ɪ – इ [ɪ] scissors - qaunci, basin - cilamci; ɪ – उ [y] wife – khatun, lady – khanum.

Assimilation of Turkism grammar

The world languages are different in grammatical structures. According to these different languages words are different in morphology structure. The internal peculiarities of language grammatical structure, in addition to say it couldn't give any influences for other languages. However this common right can be destroyed by the events of strong influence. Sometimes long communication of two countries made to change the grammatical elements.

In linguistics the language grammar structure have many arguments to take other elements. In foreign linguistics the recommendations of V.D.Witney, A. Meie, E. Sepir that there are no way of strange elements in grammar system, and G.Schukhardt, A. Rosetti gave opposite recommendation.

In the recommendation of K.M.Musaev, the language grammar system doesn't take elements of other grammatical system and their morphological typology, which is given to research the common languages. In general, the language morphological system is stable and they don't always take adopted elements. But, in one case, not similar of typology in language communication, some morphological elements may include into other languages. We are agreeing to the recommendations of U.D. Desheriev, T.A. Menovshikov, K.M. Musaev, that the grammatical system of language use other language elements.

The assimilation of noun

Many of scientists of language communication the word, taken from adopted, which in the first place is noun, at the end it is verb, and numeral is not changes into another language.

The most of part of Turkic adopted words are in female gender, small part is in male gender.

For example, the female gender words: **आपा** (apa) - *sister*, **तोप** (top) - *gun*, **जुर्रब** (jurrab) - *socks*.

Male gender words: **चोगा** (coğa) - *dressing gown*, **करावल** (qaraval) - *gun*, **कुरता** (kurta) - *cardigan* and etc.

In the process of vocabulary the adopted words has to have the main conditions. These conditions connect with requirements of words. At first, the communication of the adopted words in the process of vocabulary is carrying out in the process of agglutination and hybrid (the new words from different elements by genetics) and loan translation methods and examples.

The one of frequently used word-formation suffixes in Turkic language is the suffix **-ची** [-ci] - *ушы, -уи*. It is direct speech of Hindi and they give possibilities of connection to the adopted words in Arabian, Persia and English languages. For example, **मशलची** [mshalci] - (to Arabian word *maşal* added the suffix) *the person, who takes fire*, **रायफलची** [rayafalci] - *rifleman*, that is English word *rafle* add the suffix *-ci* and etc. The adopted words with the suffix *-ушы, -уи* **तोपची** [topci] - *artilleryman*, **एलची** [elci] - *ambassador* and others.

The assimilation of adjective

The Turkic adjectives are less in Hindi, than nouns.

The qualified adjectives from Turkic language: **कल्लाश** (qallash) - 1. *low*; 2. *very poor*; **कुमेट** (kumet) - *grey (color)*.

The relative adjectives from Turkic language: **उर्दूपन** (urdupan) - *correspondence to Urdu language*.

The assimilation of other parts of speech

Turkic language's numerals, verbs, pronouns, adverbs didn't change to Hindi at all.

Joining the Turkic words and Hindi verbs formed the derivative verb, for example, **तलाश करना** [talash karna] *to search*, **तलाश** [talash] - the noun *search* and in Hindi **करना** [karna] *to join the verb do, make forms derivative verb*. **बरमा चलाना** [barma calana] *to drill, turn, blow* **बरमा** [barma] the word *drill* and the verb **चलाना** [calana] *to drive* appeared the verb *to drill*. The verb infinitive is the morpheme **-ना** (-na) in Turkic languages **तलाश** [talash] connects to the word *search* and came out the verb **तलाशना** [talash+na (H)] *to search*.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

The communication of India and Turkic languages considered in the works of D.Kaushik, P.Jazkson, R.C. Foltz, M.N.Nuri, A.H. Khan, R. Raina. It is used to describe, typological, historico-cognitive, compare, conclude, decline, component parsing of the methods in this research work. To consider the adopted words has done semantic modeling, cognitive review methods.

A. Hypothesis

The income words of Turkic elements in Hindi had income and used. Turkic elements are used as direct speech in Hindi words. It takes an important place from other foreign language vocabularies and they used actively. Changing the Turkic language into Hindi is the result of long and difficult time process. If we look at the numbers of adopted words in Hindi, there are 100 units of adopted words from Turkic language.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Hindi language becomes rich sources of other languages vocabularies, to collect the vocabulary they took words from other languages. During the research was defined Turkic language among them.

In order to improve the purpose of the scientific work, we should pay attention to the conclusions of language communication in science. On the basis of results of useful and new methods, we can say that is appeared new direction and new scientific work. The task of the scientific work found own decision, and the object of research work is modern Hindi language vocabulary. The peculiarities of income and assimilation levels of the adopted words of Hindi will define.

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